

DESIGN CRITERIA FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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INTRODUCTION

The study of the relationship between the structure and the properties of fiber composite materials is motivated by two major desires. The first is to utilize this understanding of material behavior for the purpose of designing structures which will function with high reliability for long lifetimes. The second is to apply our understanding to the development of improved materials. Much work on such studies of physical properties of composites has been done over the last decade. As a result, a survey of the field requires a comprehensive book, rather than a review paper. Such surveys do exist to guide the interested person (e.g., References 3 through 5).

This lecture will briefly discuss the concepts involved in the study of structure/property relations for composites. It's focus will be upon some unanswered questions which are critical to the development of a high confidence design capability.

Advanced composites offer the freedom to design materials having preferential directional properties. This creates the potential of tailoring a material for a particular application. However, it leads to the complexity of a material having a large number of potential failure modes. Many of these failure modes are unlike those encountered in homogeneous materials. Thus, there is a need to develop the methodology of failure prediction for composites in order to raise the confidence level. The predictions of failure strengths and modes in the presence of imperfections (surface flaws,

inherent manufacturing defects like imperfect adhesion between layers) and discontinuities (bolted and bonded joints) is particularly complex. Though numerous attempts have been made to interpret and analyze available experimental fracture data, there is an incomplete understanding of the fracture phenomenon for composites at the present time. Added concerns for component reliability, requirements for accurate safelife prediction, and damage-tolerant design, underscore the need for a viable composite failure analysis which can give the designer a quantitative estimate of the failure stresses and a qualitative picture of damage growth.

It is important to keep in mind that, as the technology progresses, new materials will be continually coming along and it will be necessary to strive to develop an understanding which is sufficiently general to stimulate the utilization of improved materials. Thus, in addition to composite laminates of boron, graphite and other fiber reinforcements, attention must be given to materials of the types shown schematically in Figure 1. In one advanced form, hybrid composites, one is concerned with multiple reinforcement in which the different fibers may be oriented in different directions. For special applications one may utilize three-dimensional reinforcement materials. All of these geometric forms must be considered along with the use of different matrix materials which may enable us to extend the operational environment, including wider ranges of temperature at which these composites can be utilized.

In dealing with all these types of composite materials, it is essential to recognize that the capability to tailor the properties of composites makes materials design an integral part of the structural design process. The design cycle for a composite structure may be viewed as having the steps shown in Figure 2. Thus, the designer can exercise the choice of fiber and matrix material, from among a number of choices; he can select amounts of different materials; he can orient layers of fibers in different directions; he can do this differently in various elements of the structure; and, of course, he can configure the various structural elements. The design process is likely to be an interactive one at present.

This lecture concentrates upon structural properties, although many applications may be motivated by electrical, thermal or other properties of composites and this design philosophy applies equally well to such other applications.

EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES CONCEPTS

In general, composite materials cannot be blindly regarded as just another type of material. The nature of their properties are different, and it is counter-productive to attempt to force them into the mold of such simple property measures as specific strength and specific modulus. These materials do not behave as one-dimen-

sional materials; their behavior is complex and they must be viewed as such. We can, however, define effective macroscopic properties which do represent this complex nature of composites. This is suggested by the photographs of Figure 3 of the same material taken at a number of different magnifications. In the upper left, at a very high level of magnification, is an array of silicon carbide fibers embedded in a pyrolytic graphite matrix, which is a high temperature coating material (Reference 6). At that level of magnification, the constituents are identifiable; one may speak of the local constituent properties. Thus, the fibers for example, are brittle materials having a statistical strength distribution and some definable geometry. This constituent information defines the characteristic unit cell. At the next lower level of magnification, there are a large number of these unit cells in what is called a representative volume element (RVE). The RVE contains the characteristics of this material. It is at the scale of the RVE that the effective point properties of a composite material can be defined. It is at that scale that properties can be translated from the micro to the macro. The properties of the assemblage are point properties which will vary from point to point. Thus, at the next lower scale of magnification, there is an assemblage of elements in which the different elements may have different properties. This defines the statistical variability of the material on a macro scale. This assemblage is still of very small dimension compared to the material, and compared to the characteristic dimension over which any of the state variables would change significantly. Thus, statistical effects upon material properties can be defined for the assemblage and used in an analysis; for example, in a thermal stress analysis of the total coating shown in the lower left of Figure 3.

For certain purposes, it is desirable to view the material on the macro scale and to treat it as an homogeneous, anisotropic material (i.e., as having properties which differ in different directions). For other purposes, it is important to retain the fact that the constituents of this material are distinct, and that these distinctions are quite pronounced, so that the material must truly be regarded as a heterogeneous material. This is particularly important with regard to the question of strength.

Another important characteristic is variability. The objective is repeatable performance. It is desired that every time we make a component out of this material, it should behave in the same fashion. It does not follow from this that we seek absolute uniformity of material properties. If all the fibers had an absolutely uniform strength, then the entire material could fail at once. There would be no margin for error, nor would there be any capability to compensate for some of the imperfections in our design understanding. What is desired, is that the statistical distribution associated with the sample of this material shall be repeatable from batch to batch. The need for repeatability of component performance does not eliminate statistical variability on the microscale.

In order to define performance of composite materials, it is necessary to introduce the concept of effective properties. Considering the homogeneous material illustrated in the top of Figure 4 subjected to uniform stress on the boundaries, there will be a uniform state of stress in the material. When the material is heterogeneous, the lower portion of Figure 4 schematically illustrates, that on a point to point basis, there will be a significant variability of stress in the material. However, it can be shown that the mean value of the axial stress component will be equal to the applied stress component. Thus, the mean value of this stress is the appropriate state variable to be used in the stress-strain relations. The average values of stress and of strain are related by what we call the effective elastic moduli.

COMPOSITE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

This subject of elastic properties of composite materials is one that has received a substantial amount of attention in the literature. Several different analytical approaches have been utilized. Strength of materials approaches which one might have been justified in using in the early stages of dealing with these materials are no longer necessary because better tools are available. In some cases, what we know as micro-mechanics has been utilized to solve this problem as a boundary value problem. Here, all details of the internal structure material can be included; of course, in general, we do not know all of this detail. In some cases, we have a geometry that is difficult to treat, so that we would use what has come to be called a self-consistent scheme. More generally, we can look beyond the local details and work with variational methods to obtain these properties. Much work has been done in this area, and the interested reader should refer to Reference 3.

It is important to recognize that, from an analysis of basic elastic constants of the material, stems the capability to generate a wide number of other material properties. Thus, for composites of two materials, when we know the effective elastic constants of the materials, and we know the properties of the two individual constituents, there exist a set of relations which define the thermal expansion coefficients of the material. Further, when we know the elastic constants we can apply transform techniques, and can translate the elastic problem into a visco-elastic problem. From these elastic moduli, we can find effective visco-elastic properties. For example, this provides the capability to assess the complex moduli which defines the response to vibratory loads including the damping characteristics of the materials, again as a function of their constituents. Finally, by virtue of the similarities in the equations, it is possible to take the equations for shear moduli of composites as a function of those of their constituents and write down the solution to the conduction problems and get effective electrical, magnetic and thermal properties from the expressions for elastic

properties. This includes effective thermal and electrical conductivities, magnetic permeabilities, and dielectric constants. Thus, the analysis of this basic property of elastic constants is one which is important for reasons well beyond the definition of the relationship of elastic constants.

The physical properties discussed above represent aspects of the study of composites which, relatively speaking, are well understood. By no means have we solved all their problems, as is evidenced by the number of papers treating this subject at this conference, among others. However, we have a foundation; we have a starting point; we have an ability to assess, in the preliminary design phase, the anticipated relationship between properties of composites and properties of their constituents. Thus, we may conduct mathematical experiments and eliminate the need for extensive material experimentation with a wide range of material properties. By this process, we may focus our experimental effort in those areas which seem to hold the greatest promise. However, we cannot do this to the degree that we would like to do it, because these materials do not always behave in a simple fashion. Composites can behave in a nonlinear fashion because of the occurrence of internal damage or because of the fact that the matrix is non-linear. Matrix non-linearity will result in the fact that individual layers in a composite laminate will have non-linear shear and transverse stress-strain curves. It then becomes necessary to generalize our laminate analysis capability and do a non-linear analysis. Methods exist for doing this. Generally, in a practical advanced composite laminate, (which we may define as one having a high modulus fiber oriented in at least three different directions) we will find that the differences between elastic linear and the non-linear analysis will not be dramatic in terms of its overall effects; but the local stress state may vary enough to cause important differences in failure. More important, however, is the fact that as we move into the higher temperature range, we find that we are dealing with constituents whose properties may vary with temperature and at the higher temperature, stress-strain behavior may be non-linear.

The consequences of non-linear behavior are many. For example, there is the residual thermal stress problem which, for applications such as the turbine blade, may require that serious attention be given to non-linear analysis methods. We will be concerned similarly for these non-linear materials with low cycle fatigue, and with thermal fatigue, and with the redistribution of stresses associated with thermal cycling. We must always remember in treating these materials that we have a macro stress state and a micro stress state. Redistribution of the micro stress state, caused by such things as the non-linear effects of thermal cycling, may have a serious effect upon the subsequent macro behavior of these composite materials. And, when we say behavior, of course, one of the important things that we are talking about is the static strength of these materials. By static strength we mean strength under a combination of loads in

different directions. Practical engineering structures have primary load conditions which may be unidirectional, but they will also have other stress states. These are stress states which may, for metals, be regarded as secondary stress states; but for these materials, which have high differences in properties associated with different directions, these secondary stress states may become quite important. Thus, we have had to develop failure criteria for interaction among stress states. We are familiar with criteria such as maximum stress, maximum strain, quadratic interaction, Tsai-Wu, etc. These are mathematical models for describing the inter-relationship among different stress components contributing to the failure of a unidirectional layer of composite materials. The interested reader is referred to References 4 and 5 for a full discussion of these criteria.

Emphasis herein is placed upon the use of physical models, in the belief that we do not understand the behavior of these materials if we simply have a fit between a mathematical expression and some experimental data. Indeed, it seems puzzling to observe that the "composites community" is so eager to accept the conclusion that, when experiment and analysis are in agreement, both the experiment and the analysis are correct. With these materials, we must challenge the experimental methods that were used and we must ask many questions about the physical realities of the mathematical models that we use. That is not to say that we should stop; but is to say that as we proceed with the advancement of technology, we proceed with the advancement of understanding, so that truly in the future we will have the necessary capability for both experimental and theoretical aspects of the problem.

MATERIAL FAILURE

The failure criteria for an individual layer can be used with a laminate stress analysis to provide laminate failure criteria. Large differences in lamina strengths in tension and compression, lead to the unbalanced shape of the laminate failure surface shown in Figure 5. This curve is for combined loads for a relatively simple cross-ply laminate, and it results from a quadratic failure criterion being utilized as the definition of failure for a single layer in this composite. The question relative to the surface is: is it truly representative and can the underlying methodology be applied to a material for which we do not yet have a data base? Before this question can be answered, it is necessary for us to look at what it is that causes laminate failure.

UNIAXIAL TENSION AND COMPRESSION

Figure 6 provides a schematic of an axial tension failure mode. Here a set of unidirectional fibers is embedded in a matrix material with the composite under a tensile stress in the fiber direction.

The fibers (simple cross hatching) are in the clear matrix and the dark lines represent cracks. The cracks occur in different places in the composite material because the fibers are nonuniform in their strength distribution. When a fiber breaks, there is a stress concentration region in the vicinity of the broken fiber: both in shear, causing some local areas of high shear deformation (double cross hatching) and in extension in the adjacent fiber material. As a result of these stress concentrations, the cracks may grow locally in size, as load is increased, as well as in number. This accumulation of areas of damage will eventually lead to a failure that may occur either in the form of a weakening of the overall material, or in an unstable crack propagation from one of these growing crack areas. The mode of failure will be determined by the nature of both constituents and the interaction between them.

Figure 7 shows the same model from an experiment in which photoelastic methods are used to demonstrate the stress concentrations that result. This is a unidirectional fiber composite with a series of closely spaced fibers. When a fiber breaks we get an unloading locally of the fiber which is represented by a dark fringe in this photoelastic pattern. The local shear stresses transfer the load that was in that fiber into the adjacent fiber (producing a stress concentration) and then back into the broken fiber on the other side of the break. Thus, there is an ineffective region of fiber, a stress concentration and high local shear stresses. A distribution of fiber breaks resulting from the statistical variability of the material exists. These breaks accumulate rather than propagate because of the toughness of the matrix material and its ability to carry shear stresses. Multiple adjacent breaks do occur because of the stress concentration. This cumulative weakening is the probable mechanism of failure mode in tension in brittle-fiber composites, particularly those in which there is some significant coefficient of variation of individual fiber or yarn strengths.

Thus, there are a number of different possible failure mechanisms contributing to composite failure. There is the possibility of the high shear stresses causing interface separation; the possibility of the high extensional stresses causing a crack propagation; and the possibility of the damage zones due to the material variabilities accumulating. In reality, combinations of all of these modes are to be expected. On the other hand, when these materials are loaded in compression, we see a very different failure phenomenon. Figure 8 shows a set of three single glass fibers embedded in blocks of epoxy. The photoelastic fringe patterns illustrate a fiber micro buckling, analogous to a classical buckling of a column on an elastic foundation. The same phenomenon is shown for three blocks of epoxy. In such a micro instability, the failure stress level is strongly influenced by the nature of the matrix material. The instability may also be strongly influenced by the fiber properties. An SEM photo of Kevlar-49 fibers is shown in Figure 9. Here, shear bands and a fibrillation of the fiber indicate an internal instability of the

fiber as something contributing to the failure mode in compression.

Combined Stresses

The various failure mechanisms for loads in the fiber direction are very different. Additionally, shear failure and transverse failure would involve different mechanisms. Thus, there does not seem to be a physical justification for using a mathematical polynomial and saying that it represents the interaction of these combined stresses which individually produce such markedly different failure behavior.

Some attempts have been made to generate "physically based" material failure criteria (e.g., Ref. 7). In Figure 10, two "physically based" failure surfaces are presented. The dotted line is a maximum strain failure criterion and the solid line is the MSC criterion (Ref. 8). These two failure surfaces, which are plotted for a $0/+45^\circ$ laminate, are very close together. However, a "mathematical" failure surface presented in Figure 11, has quite a different appearance. At this stage, these differences serve only to reflect the limitations on our understanding of failure of composites.

Fatigue

The failure problem becomes even more complex when we look at environments other than the simple static loading environment. Failure mechanisms will be influenced by the nature of the loading condition. This is illustrated in Figure 12, which shows $0/+45^\circ$ boron/epoxy laminates with 0.25" and 0.50" central slit notches. For static loads, the mode of failure in both cases was transverse crack propagation; the type of failure which would occur in a metal. Figure 13 shows results for the same laminates subjected to tension fatigue loading. Hence, the shear stresses at the notch tip caused axial cracking to propagate. This blunts the extensional stress concentration and prevents the occurrence of two part failure of the specimen.

This indicates the need for a better definition of failure. There is a need to define the residual property of a composite material at some point in its lifetime; that is the capability of the laminate to withstand its design load after it has gone through a portion of its lifetime. Design criteria for these materials differ from those that were formerly used for metals.

Design Criteria

A common approach to defining allowable material stresses is to utilize factors of safety, as suggested schematically in Figure 14.

In this case, we said that if we had a stress strain curve, as shown on the left, and an S-N curve for fatigue as shown on the right, that we could select an ultimate load factor, a limit load factor, and a lifetime factor. Then we could go from these deterministic curves to the definition of the allowable stresses to use in our design process. But we should recognize material variability; particularly in the aerospace industry, we define our material properties in terms of statistical allowables for static strength. In the fatigue area, we have the same problem. Thus when we seek an S-N curve, we will get a distribution of lifetimes from the specimens that we test and therefore we should take contours representing given probability levels associated with this stress level. This is suggested in Figure 15. In order to do that, we recognize the physical reality of the fact that if a material does not fail under the first static application of a load and it does fail under very many applications of the same load; it follows that during the subsequent applications of this load we have caused some damage to the material. This gradual deterioration of the material produces fatigue failure. In the case of metallic alloys, the effect on properties of this deterioration is not readily apparent until fatigue failure is imminent. In the case of composite materials, this change in properties can be a much more pronounced phenomenon. Thus, since we are interested in how long something lasts, we should examine residual properties after exposure to the loading environment for some period of time. We should plot on a time scale the residual static strength of the material (see Figure 16). Because there is variability in lifetime, there will be variability in residual strength. Because there is gradual degradation, the properties of the material will change with time. The combination of these effects means that we need to take our statistics and draw curves of constant probability through the residual strength.

Figure 17 (from Reference 9) emphasizes the fact that static strength and life time are part of the same design phenomenon; that is at zero time we recognize that there is an initial variability in the strength of the material. As we apply some loads as experienced by the structure during its lifetime, the initial imperfections (or the initial characteristics which resulted in this initial statistical variability) will result in the propagation or growth of damage. The damage will grow for these different specimens at different rates and there will be a continual deterioration as represented by the band of residual strength properties as a function of time. Finally the residual strength will decay to the point where it is equal to the applied load and failure will occur. Fatigue failure, in this concept, is the situation in which the residual strength has been reduced by repeated load applications to the level of the applied load. This concept, which has been described by the name "wearout", has as its major characteristics the following concepts: failure is caused by existing flaws; flaws extend in a known manner under repeated loads; increased flaw size causes decreased material strength. Thus, the statistical variability of a material

in its fabricated form is a result of a statistical distribution of existing flaws in the material. These flaws under repeated exposure to various aspects to the environment will extend in some fashion. The increased size and number of these damage areas and flaws will result in decreased material strength after some time.

However, for composites it is not enough to say that repeated loads will result in a change in strength. It is also necessary to say that existing flaws may propagate in different directions. For metals, there is a methodology developed based on classical fracture mechanics to characterize this process. That is, there are initial flaw effects; the fracture strength of a flawed material can be related to the initial crack dimension; and flaw growth with time is proportional to some power of the flaw size. As the flaw size changes, so does the residual strength. Thus, strength becomes a function of service lifetime.

This phenomenon is illustrated schematically in Figure 18. There is a statistical variability of strength among the members of a set of specimens of a given composite. We say that there is a one to one relationship between the strength variability and the variability of some internal damage in the micro crack. We say that when loads are applied these cracks will grow so that after some time the distribution of damage will be different from the initial distribution of damage and the one to one relationship between internal damage and strength means that there will be a new strength distribution that differs from the initial strength distribution. Flaw sizes will grow, strength will decrease, and wearout or change in residual characteristics is the end result.

Classical fracture mechanics has been able to give us a tool for developing a reliability based methodology for working with metal composites.

The question here is how do composites behave relative to wearout? A major difference is that we may have non-colinear crack growth. The direction of the crack growth in a composite will be very strongly influenced by the planes of weakness associated with the orientation of fibers in a composite laminate. We will experience changes in matrix properties due to environmental degradation. These factors together will result in wearout. The methodology here is being applied to the question of wearout of strength properties; it is equally important to recognize that there will be changes in material stiffness and changes in material damping and therefore we will have the residual performance capability as the question that we must address. There are structures which are stiffness critical, there are structures which have flutter problems and thus we must define the residual performance capability whether it be after fatigue, after exposure to environment, after exposure to impact, etc.

Several alternatives exist for composite fracture. One is to add another parameter to the classical mechanics equations. For

example, a characteristic dimension which has come to be called the intense energy region has been used. With this modification one can attempt to fit the data using two parameters in the system. Depending upon the nature of the material system this may or may not lead to some success. At best it appears that this will classify the experimental data that have already been obtained. This may be adequate for some design purposes. However, in order to understand why the materials are behaving as they do so that we can design improved materials, I suggest that it is necessary to look at the modes of failure of these materials.

In order to do that, some of my colleagues and myself have utilized a model of the type shown in Figure 19. The unique factor that we emphasize here is that this notch has a region at its end in which we will treat the possibility of non colinear crack growth. Not only do we have the possibility of propagation in the classical sense, we also have what might be called a crack arrest. Indeed much effort has gone into deliberately introducing crack arrest mechanisms into some advanced composites. We must be able to model these phenomena. What happens when you do this is illustrated schematically in Figure 20. Here a defect is represented by a slit notch of width $2a$. When load is applied to the notched composite there are some highly stressed regions near the notch. In those regions the matrix may experience changes in its shear properties as a function of time (number of cycles). The change in properties near the notch as a result of fatigue will result in a redistribution of stresses. The redistribution of stress will cause a change in the existing damage mechanisms and may result in extension of an axial crack, α , which may grow in this material.

This leads us to the statistical considerations suggested in Figure 21 in which we recognize that the material has variability. As time goes on we may get a local change in shear properties. As a consequence of this there will be a local change in geometry of the defect. To address this growth of damage, the proper variable in a statistical sense is time to failure. The expected time to first failure of one of the components that we have is an important design factor, as is the distribution of time to failure. Illustrated in Figure 21 is the capability of eliminating some of the bad members of the population due to initial nondestructive inspection. Also there is the possibility of removing other serious defects by proof testing. The objective is to end up with a material in which the crack growth, as shown in the right, yields a safe crack growth life; that is, it does not grow to critical size until we get to the desired lifetime of the component. One of the problems with this approach utilizing the proof test is the fact that with the multiplicity of failure mechanisms in a composite material we cannot be assured that the defect which is most critical for static strength will be the defect which is most critical after some exposure to fatigue. That is a direct result of the fact that different defects in composites can grow at different rates.

This important effect is illustrated in Figure 22. Here is plot of the stress in the load direction at the tip of a notch. There are two different notch sizes, a large initial flaw (A) and a smaller initial flaw (B). As stress is increased, the stress concentration causes increasing stress until there is some growth of an axial damage mechanism. This may be a non-elastic shear deformation, or it may be actual axial cracking at the edge of a notch. The blunting of the stress concentration factor may result in a rounding of the notch tip stress curve. If this prevents the maximum stress from exceeding the strength or the adjacent material, the end result may be extensive propagation of the axial crack. In the case shown, if the strength of the material at the notch tip is between the peaks of the two curves then crack A will fail by axial propagation, whereas crack B will fail due to transverse propagation. Thus different modes of failure may grow differently for different size defects and thus it will become necessary to address the question of distribution of the initial defect size not simply to the question of screening out the bad static ones. What is required here is some effort to identify modes of failure associated with various types of materials. An initial static strength distribution does not define initial flaw distribution in a unique fashion because of these different failure modes. Cracks will grow at different rates; current methods imply inherently some unique relationship which may not exist for composite materials and hence the proof test concept can be questionable for this. We need a modified wearout model. Above all we need to recognize the differences in the behavior between the fiber composite laminates and their metal counterparts.

In summary, I have tried to demonstrate that a good understanding of many physical properties exist. Also, that it is necessary to recognize in many of these physical properties, that statistical variability is inherent in these materials. The design objective is reproducibility of performance, not necessarily absolute uniformity of all properties of all constituents. We must look beyond the simple correlations between experiment and theory to make sure that our experiments are truly measuring the properties that we need to use for design, and to seek both a mathematical and physical understanding. The emphasis for reliability of performance, for many properties important to the designer must be placed upon residual performance capability. Above all I hope that I have been able to communicate the message that materials design is closely linked to component design and both must be carried out in a coordinated and integrated fashion.

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FIGURE 1. ADVANCED FORMS OF COMPOSITE CONSTRUCTION

FIGURE 2. THE DESIGN CYCLE FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

S.E.M. 10,000X
a. CONSTITUENTS

S.E.M. 1000X
b. REPRESENTATIVE VOLUME ELEMENT

S.E.M. 50X
d. GRADED COATING

S.E.M. 200X
c. ASSEMBLAGE OF ELEMENTS

FIGURE 3. MATERIAL MODELLING

FIGURE 4. STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS ON A MICRO-SCALE AND ON A MACRO-SCALE

FIGURE 5. QUADRATIC FAILURE SURFACE, Gr/Ep [0/90]

FIGURE 6. DISTRIBUTION OF DAMAGE IN A FIBER COMPOSITE MATERIAL RESULTING FROM AN APPLIED LOAD

FIGURE 7. PHOTOELASTIC STRESS PATTERN SHOWING
DISTRIBUTED FIBER FRACTURES IN A
GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITE UNDER TENSILE
LOADING

FIGURE 8. PHOTOELASTIC STRESS PATTERN SHOWING FIBER MICROBUCKLING

FIGURE 9. COMPRESSIVE FAILURE WITHIN INDIVIDUAL FIBERS OF A KEVLAR-49/EPOXY COMPOSITE

FIGURE 10. MSC/HET and MAX ϵ FAILURE SURFACE, Gr/Ep [0+45]

Figure 11. Coordinate Intersections of QUAD Failure Surface, $G_r/E_p[0/+45]$, Tangent Modulus.

FIGURE 12. STATIC FAILURE OF NOTCHED $[\pm 45/0_2]$
BORON-EPOXY LAMINATES

(a) 0.25" NOTCH

(b) 0.50" NOTCH

FIGURE 13. FATIGUE DAMAGE OF NOTCHED $[\pm 45/0_2]$ BORON-EPOXY LAMINATES

STATIC

FATIGUE

FIGURE 14. DESIGN VIA FACTORS OF SAFETY

FIGURE 15. LIFETIME RELIABILITY

FAILURE: $\sigma_{\text{APPLIED}} = \sigma_{\text{RESIDUAL}}$

FIGURE 16. RESIDUAL STRENGTH

FIGURE 17. RELATIONSHIP AMONG STATIC STRENGTH, RESIDUAL STRENGTH, AND TIME TO FAILURE (Reference 9)

FIGURE 18. TRANSLATION FROM STATIC DOMAIN TO FATIGUE DOMAIN

FIGURE 19. 'MATERIALS ENGINEERING' MODEL FOR A NOTCHED LAMINATE

FIGURE 20. FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH

1. ASSUME INITIAL FLAW DISTRIBUTION.
 2. ELIMINATE DETECTABLE FLAWS BY NON-DESTRUCTIVE INSPECTION.
 3. ESTABLISH B ALLOWABLE.
- or
4. GUARANTEE NO FLAW ABOVE A GIVEN SIZE (A) BY PROOF TESTING.

1. DEVELOP FLAW GROWTH MODEL.
2. ESTABLISH SAFE CRACK GROWTH LIFE.

FIGURE 21. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INITIAL FLAW DISTRIBUTION AND SUBSEQUENT DAMAGE GROWTH (from Reference 9)

FIGURE 22. CHANGE IN NOTCH TIP STRESS AND AXIAL CRACK GROWTH FOR DIFFERENT SIZE INITIAL CRACKS